

The New Generalized Difference of χ^2 over p - Metric Spaces Defined by Musielak Orlicz Function

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Abstract. We introduce new sequence spaces by using Musielak-Orlicz function and a generalized B_{η}^{μ} -difference operator or p -metric space. Some topological properties are studied.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout w, χ and Λ denote the classes of all, gai and analytic scalar valued single sequences, respectively.

We write w^2 for the set of all complex sequences (x_{mn}) , where $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, the set of positive integers. Then, w^2 is a linear space under the coordinate wise addition and scalar multiplication.

Some initial works on double sequence spaces is found in Bromwich [1]. Later on it was investigated by Hardy [2], Moricz [3], Moricz and Rhoades [4], Basarir and Solankan [5], Tripathy et al., [6-10], Turkmenoglu [11], Raj [12-14] and many others.

Let (x_{mn}) be a double sequence of real or complex numbers. Then the series $\sum_{m,n=1}^{\infty} x_{mn}$ is called a double series. The double series $\sum_{m,n=1}^{\infty} x_{mn}$ give one space is said to be convergent if and only if the double sequence (S_{mn}) is convergent, where

$$S_{mn} = \sum_{i,j=1}^{m,n} x_{ij} (m, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots) .$$

A double sequence $x = (x_{mn})$ is said to be double analytic if

$$\sup_{m,n} |x_{mn}|^{\frac{1}{m+n}} < \infty.$$

The vector space of all double analytic sequences are usually denoted by Λ^2 . A sequence $x = (x_{mn})$ is called double entire sequence if

$$|x_{mn}|^{\frac{1}{m+n}} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } m, n \rightarrow \infty.$$

The vector space of all double entire sequences are usually denoted by Γ^2 . Let the set of sequences with this property be denoted by Λ^2 and Γ^2 is a metric space with the metric

$$(1.1) \quad d(x, y) = \sup_{m,n} \left\{ |x_{mn} - y_{mn}|^{\frac{1}{m+n}} : m, n : 1, 2, 3, \dots \right\},$$

for all $x = \{x_{mn}\}$ and $y = \{y_{mn}\}$ in Γ^2 . Let $\phi = \{\text{finite sequences}\}$.

Consider a double sequence $x = (x_{mn})$. The $(m, n)^{th}$ section $x^{[m,n]}$ of the sequence is defined by $x^{[m,n]} = \sum_{i,j=0}^{m,n} x_{ij} \delta_{ij}$ for all $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\delta_{mn} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ \cdot & & & & & \\ \cdot & & & & & \\ \cdot & & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots \end{pmatrix}$$

with 1 in the $(m, n)^{th}$ position and zero otherwise.

A double sequence $x = (x_{mn})$ is called double gai sequence if $((m+n)! |x_{mn}|)^{\frac{1}{m+n}} \rightarrow 0$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$. The double gai sequences will be denoted by χ^2 .

Let M and Φ be mutually complementary Orlicz functions. Then, we have

(i) For all $u, y \geq 0$,

$$(1.2) \quad uy \leq M(u) + \Phi(y), \text{ (Young's inequality) [See [Kamphanetal., [15]]]}$$

(ii) For all $u \geq 0$,

$$(1.3) \quad u\eta(u) = M(u) + \Phi(\eta(u)).$$

(iii) For all $u \geq 0$, and $0 < \lambda < 1$,

$$(1.4) \quad M(\lambda u) \leq \lambda M(u).$$

Lindenstrauss and Tzafiri [16] used the idea of Orlicz function to construct Orlicz sequence space

$$\ell_M = \left\{ x \in w : \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} M\left(\frac{|x_k|}{\rho}\right) < \infty, \text{ for some } \rho > 0 \right\},$$

The space ℓ_M with the norm

$$\|x\| = \inf \left\{ \rho > 0 : \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} M\left(\frac{|x_k|}{\rho}\right) \leq 1 \right\},$$

becomes a Banach space which is called an Orlicz sequence space. For $M(t) = t^p$ ($1 \leq p < \infty$), the spaces ℓ_M coincide with the classical sequence space ℓ_p .

A sequence $f = (f_{mn})$ of Orlicz function is called a Musielak-Orlicz function. A sequence $g = (g_{mn})$ defined by

$$g_{mn}(v) = \sup \{|v|u - f_{mn}(u) : u \geq 0\}, m, n = 1, 2, \dots$$

is called the complementary function of a Musielak-Orlicz function f . For a given Musielak Orlicz function f , the Musielak-Orlicz sequence space t_f is defined by

$$t_f = \left\{ x \in w^2 : I_f(|x_{mn}|)^{1/m+n} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } m, n \rightarrow \infty \right\},$$

where I_f is a convex modular defined by

$$I_f(x) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_{mn}(|x_{mn}|)^{1/m+n}, x = (x_{mn}) \in t_f.$$

We consider t_f equipped with the Luxemburg metric

$$d(x, y) = \sup_{mn} \left\{ \inf \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_{mn} \left(\frac{|x_{mn} - y_{mn}|^{1/m+n}}{mn} \right) \leq 1 \right) \right\}.$$

The notion of difference sequence spaces (for single sequences) was introduced by Kizmaz [16] as follows

$$Z(\Delta) = \{x = (x_k) \in w : (\Delta x_k) \in Z\},$$

for $Z = c, c_0$ and ℓ_{∞} , where $\Delta x_k = x_k - x_{k+1}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Here c, c_0 and ℓ_{∞} denote the classes of convergent, null and bounded scalar valued single sequences respectively. The spaces $c(\Delta), c_0(\Delta), \ell_{\infty}(\Delta)$ and bv_p are Banach spaces normed by

$$\|x\| = |x_1| + \sup_{k \geq 1} |\Delta x_k| \text{ and } \|x\|_{bv_p} = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |x_k|^p \right)^{1/p}, (1 \leq p < \infty).$$

Later on the notion was further investigated by many others. We now introduce the following difference double sequence spaces defined by

$$Z(\Delta) = \{x = (x_{mn}) \in w^2 : (\Delta x_{mn}) \in Z\},$$

where $Z = \Lambda^2, \chi^2$ and $\Delta x_{mn} = (x_{mn} - x_{mn+1}) - (x_{m+1n} - x_{m+1n+1}) = x_{mn} - x_{mn+1} - x_{m+1n} + x_{m+1n+1}$ for all $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$. The generalized difference double notion has the following representation: $\Delta^m x_{mn} = \Delta^{m-1} x_{mn} - \Delta^{m-1} x_{mn+1} - \Delta^{m-1} x_{m+1n} + \Delta^{m-1} x_{m+1n+1}$, and also this generalized difference double notion has the following binomial representation: $\Delta^m x_{mn} = \sum_{i=0}^m \sum_{j=0}^m (-1)^{i+j} \binom{m}{i} \binom{m}{j} x_{m+i, n+j}$.

Let $\eta = (\eta_{mn})$ be a sequence of nonzero scalars. Then, for a sequence space E , the multiplier sequence space E_{η} , associated with the multiplier sequence η , is defined as

$$E_{\eta} = \{x = (x_{mn}) \in w^2 : (\eta_{mn} x_{mn}) \in E\}.$$

2. DEFINITION AND PRELIMINARIES

Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and X be a real vector space of dimension w , where $n \leq w$. A real valued function $d_p(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \|(d_1(x_1, 0), \dots, d_n(x_n, 0))\|_p$ on X satisfying the following four conditions:

- (i) $\|(d_1(x_1, 0), \dots, d_n(x_n, 0))\|_p = 0$ if and only if $d_1(x_1, 0), \dots, d_n(x_n, 0)$ are linearly dependent,

- (ii) $\|(d_1(x_1, 0), \dots, d_n(x_n, 0))\|_p$ is invariant under permutation,
 - (iii) $\|(\alpha d_1(x_1, 0), \dots, d_n(x_n, 0))\|_p = |\alpha| \|(d_1(x_1, 0), \dots, d_n(x_n, 0))\|_p, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}$
 - (iv) $d_p((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \cdots (x_n, y_n)) = (d_X(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^p + d_Y(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)^p)^{1/p}$ for $1 \leq p < \infty$;
 - (or)
 - (v) $d((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)) := \sup \{d_X(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), d_Y(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)\}$,
- for $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n \in Y$ is called the p product metric of the Cartesian product of n metric spaces is the p norm of the n -vector of the norms of the n subspaces.

A trivial example of p product metric of n metric space is the p norm space is $X = \mathbb{R}$ equipped with the following Euclidean metric in the product space is the p norm:

$$\|(d_1(x_1, 0), \dots, d_n(x_n, 0))\|_E = \sup (|\det(d_{mn}(x_{mn}))|) = \sup \left(\begin{vmatrix} d_{11}(x_{11}, 0) & d_{12}(x_{12}, 0) & \dots & d_{1n}(x_{1n}, 0) \\ d_{21}(x_{21}, 0) & d_{22}(x_{22}, 0) & \dots & d_{2n}(x_{2n}, 0) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ d_{n1}(x_{n1}, 0) & d_{n2}(x_{n2}, 0) & \dots & d_{nn}(x_{nn}, 0) \end{vmatrix} \right)$$

where $x_i = (x_{i1}, \dots, x_{in}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

If every Cauchy sequence in X converges to some $L \in X$, then X is said to be complete with respect to the p - metric. Any complete p - metric space is said to be p - Banach metric space.

Let X be a linear metric space. A function $w : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called paranorm, if

- (1) $w(x) \geq 0$, for all $x \in X$;
- (2) $w(-x) = w(x)$, for all $x \in X$;
- (3) $w(x + y) \leq w(x) + w(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$;
- (4) If (σ_{mn}) is a sequence of scalars with $\sigma_{mn} \rightarrow \sigma$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$ and (x_{mn}) is a sequence of vectors with $w(x_{mn} - x) \rightarrow 0$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$, then $w(\sigma_{mn}x_{mn} - \sigma x) \rightarrow 0$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$.

A paranorm w for which $w(x) = 0$ implies $x = 0$ is called total paranorm and the pair (X, w) is called a total paranormed space. It is well known that the metric of any linear metric space is given by some total paranorm by Willansky [17].

$\eta = (\varphi_{rs})$ a nondecreasing sequence of positive reals tending to infinity and $\varphi_{11} = 1$ and $\varphi_{r+1,s+1} \leq \varphi_{rs} + 1$.

The generalized de la Vallee-Poussin means is defined by :

$$t_{rs}(x) = \frac{1}{\varphi_{rs}} \sum_{m \in I_{rs}} \sum_{n \in I_{rs}} x_{mn},$$

where $I_{rs} = [rs - \lambda_{rs} + 1, rs]$. For the set of sequences that are strongly summable to zero, strongly summable and strongly bounded by the de la Vallee-Poussin method.

The notion of λ - double gai and double analytic sequences as follows: Let $\lambda = (\lambda_{mn})_{m,n=0}^{\infty}$ be a strictly increasing sequences of positive real numbers tending to infinity, that is

$$0 < \lambda_{00} < \lambda_{11} < \dots \text{ and } \lambda_{mn} \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } m, n \rightarrow \infty$$

and said that a sequence $x = (x_{mn}) \in w^2$ is λ - convergent to 0, called a the λ - limit of x , if $B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x) \rightarrow 0$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$, where

$$B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x) = \frac{1}{\varphi_{rs}} \sum_{m \in I_{rs}} \sum_{n \in I_{rs}} (\Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m,n} - \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m,n+1} - \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m+1,n} + \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m+1,n+1}) |x_{mn}|^{1/m+n}.$$

The sequence $x = (x_{mn}) \in w^2$ is λ - double analytic if $\sup |B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x)| < \infty$. If $\lim_{m,n} x_{mn} = 0$ in the ordinary sense of convergence, then

$$\lim_{rs} \frac{1}{\varphi_{rs}} \sum_{m \in I_{rs}} \sum_{n \in I_{rs}} (\Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m,n} - \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m,n+1} - \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m+1,n} + \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m+1,n+1}) ((m+n)! |x_{mn} - 0|)^{1/m+n} = 0.$$

This implies that

$$\lim_{rs} |B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x) - 0| = \lim_{rs} \frac{1}{\varphi_{rs}} \sum_{m \in I_{rs}} \sum_{n \in I_{rs}} (\Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m,n} - \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m,n+1} - \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m+1,n} + \Delta^{m-1} \lambda_{m+1,n+1}) ((m+n)! |x_{mn} - 0|)^{1/m+n} = 0.$$

which yields that $\lim_{uv} \mu_{mn}(x) = 0$ and hence $x = (x_{mn}) \in w^2$ is λ - convergent to 0.

Let $f = (f_{mn})$ be a Musielak-Orlicz function and $(X, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p)$ be a p -metric space, $q = (q_{mn})$ be double analytic sequence of strictly positive real numbers. By $w^2(p-X)$ we denote the space of all sequences defined over $(X, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p)$. The following inequality will be used throughout the paper. If $0 \leq q_{mn} \leq \sup q_{mn} = H, K = \max(1, 2^{H-1})$ then

$$(2.1) \quad |a_{mn} + b_{mn}|^{q_{mn}} \leq K \{|a_{mn}|^{q_{mn}} + |b_{mn}|^{q_{mn}}\}$$

for all m, n and $a_{mn}, b_{mn} \in \mathbb{C}$. Also $|a|^{q_{mn}} \leq \max(1, |a|^H)$ for all $a \in \mathbb{C}$.

Let $(X, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p)$ be an p - metric space and let $s(w^2 - x)$ denote the space of X - valued sequences. Let $q = (q_{mn})$ be any bounded sequence of positive real numbers and $f = (f_{mn})$ be a Musielak-Orlicz function. We define the following sequence spaces in this paper:

$$\left[\chi_{f B_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right]^V = \left\{ x = (x_{mn}) \in s(w^2 - x) : \lim_{rs} \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1), d(x_2), \dots, d(x_{n-1}))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} = 0 \right\},$$

$$\left[\Lambda_{f B_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right]^V = \left\{ x = (x_{mn}) \in s(w^2 - x) : \sup_{rs} \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} < \infty \right\},$$

If we take $f_{mn}(x) = x$, we get

$$\left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V = \left\{ x = (x_{mn}) \in s(w^2 - x) : \lim_{rs} \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} = 0 \right\},$$

$$\left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V = \left\{ x = (x_{mn}) \in s(w^2 - x) : \sup_{rs} \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} < \infty \right\},$$

If we take $q = (q_{mn}) = 1$, we get

$$\left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^2, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V = \left\{ x = (x_{mn}) \in s(w^2 - x) : \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right] = 0 \right\},$$

$$\left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^2, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V = \left\{ x = (x_{mn}) \in s(w^2 - x) : \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right] < \infty \right\},$$

In the present paper we plan, some topological properties are studied in the following sequence

spaces. $\left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V$ and $\left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V$ which we shall discuss in this paper.

3. MAIN RESULTS

3.1. Theorem. Let $f = (f_{mn})$ be a Musielak-Orlicz function, $q = (q_{mn})$ be a double analytic sequence of strictly positive real numbers, the sequence space

$\left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V$ is a paranormed space with respect to the paranorm defined by

$$g(x) = \inf \left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \leq 1 \right\} = 0.$$

Proof: Clearly $g(x) \geq 0$ for $x = (x_{mn}) \in \left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|(d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V$. Since $f_{mn}(0) = 0$, we get $g(0) = 0$.

Conversely, suppose that $g(x) = 0$, then

$$\inf \left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \leq 1 \right\} = 0$$

Suppose that $B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x) \neq 0$ for each $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \rightarrow \infty$. It follows that $\left(\left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \right)^{1/H} \rightarrow \infty$ which is a contradiction. Therefore $B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x) = 0$. Let

$$\left(\left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \right)^{1/H} \leq 1$$

and

$$\left(\left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(y), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \right)^{1/H} \leq 1$$

Then by using Minkowski's inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x+y), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \right)^{1/H} \leq \\ & \left(\left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \right)^{1/H} + \\ & \left(\left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(y), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \right)^{1/H}. \end{aligned}$$

So we have

$$\begin{aligned} g(x+y) &= \inf \left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x+y), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \leq 1 \right\} \leq \\ & \inf \left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \leq 1 \right\} + \\ & \inf \left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(y), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \leq 1 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$g(x+y) \leq g(x) + g(y).$$

Finally, to prove that the scalar multiplication is continuous. Let λ be any complex number. By definition,

$$g(\lambda x) = \inf \left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(\lambda x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \leq 1 \right\}.$$

Then

$$g(\lambda x) = \inf \left\{ (|\lambda|t)^{q_{mn}/H} : \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(\lambda x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \leq 1 \right\}$$

where $t = \frac{1}{|\lambda|}$. Since $|\lambda|^{q_{mn}} \leq \max(1, |\lambda|^{supq_{mn}})$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} g(\lambda x) &\leq \max(1, |\lambda|^{supq_{mn}}) \inf \\ & \left\{ t^{q_{mn}/H} : \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(\lambda x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \leq 1 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

3.2. Theorem. (i) If the sequence (f_{mn}) satisfies uniform Δ_2 - condition, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^{V\alpha} = \\ & \left[\chi_g^{2qB_{\eta}^{\mu}}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) If the sequence (g_{mn}) satisfies uniform Δ_2 - condition, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\chi_g^{2qB_{\eta}^{\mu}}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^{V\alpha} = \\ & \left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let the sequence (f_{mn}) satisfies uniform Δ_2 - condition, we get

$$(3.1) \quad \left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V \subset \left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^{V\alpha}$$

To prove the inclusion

$$\left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^{V\alpha} \subset$$

$$\left[\chi_g^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V,$$

let $a \in \left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$. Then for all $\{x_{mn}\}$ with $(x_{mn}) \in$

$$\left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V \text{ we have}$$

$$(3.2) \quad \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |x_{mn} a_{mn}| < \infty.$$

Since the sequence (f_{mn}) satisfies uniform Δ_2 - condition, then

$$(y_{mn}) \in \left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V,$$

we get $\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{\varphi_{rs} y_{mn} a_{mn}}{\Delta^m \lambda_{mn} (m+n)!} \right| < \infty$. by (3.2). Thus

$$(\varphi_{rs} a_{mn}) \in \left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V =$$

$$\left[\chi_g^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V \text{ and hence}$$

$$(a_{mn}) \in \left[\chi_g^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V. \text{ This gives that}$$

$$(3.3) \quad \left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^{V\alpha} \subset \left[\chi_g^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$$

we are granted with (3.1) and (3.3)

$$\left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^{V\alpha} =$$

$$\left[\chi_g^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$$

$$(ii) \text{ Similarly, one can prove that } \left[\chi_g^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^{V\alpha} \subset \left[\chi_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$$

if the sequence (g_{mn}) satisfies uniform Δ_2 - condition.

3.3. Proposition. If $f = (f_{mn})$ be any Musielak Orlicz function. Then

$$\left[\Lambda_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^*} \right]^V \subset$$

$$\left[\Lambda_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^{**}} \right]^V \text{ if and only if } \sup_{r,s \geq 1} \frac{\varphi_{rs}^*}{\varphi_{rs}^{**}} < \infty.$$

Proof: Let $x \in \left[\Lambda_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^*} \right]^V$ and $N = \sup_{r,s \geq 1} \frac{\varphi_{rs}^*}{\varphi_{rs}^{**}} <$

∞ . Then we get

$$\left[\Lambda_{f_{B_\eta^\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^{**}} \right]^V =$$

$$N \left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi_{rs}^*} \right]^V = 0.$$

Thus $x \in \left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^{**}} \right]^V$. Conversely, suppose that

$$\left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^*} \right]^V \subset$$

$$\left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^{**}} \right]^V \text{ and}$$

$x \in \left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^*} \right]^V$. Then

$\left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^*} \right]^V < \epsilon$, for every $\epsilon > 0$. Suppose that $\sup_{r,s \geq 1} \frac{\varphi_{rs}^*}{\varphi_{rs}^{**}} = \infty$, then there exists a sequence of members (rs_{jk}) such that $\lim_{j,k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\varphi_{jk}^*}{\varphi_{jk}^{**}} = \infty$. Hence, we have

$$\left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi_{rs}^*} \right]^V = \infty. \text{ Therefore}$$

$x \notin \left[\Lambda_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi^{**}} \right]^V$, which is a contradiction. This completes the proof.

3.4. Proposition. The sequence space $\left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V$ is not solid

Proof: The result follows from the following example.

Example: Consider

$$x = (x_{mn}) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ \cdot & & & \\ \cdot & & & \\ \cdot & & & \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in \left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V. \text{ Let}$$

$$\alpha_{mn} = \begin{pmatrix} -1^{m+n} & -1^{m+n} & \dots & -1^{m+n} \\ -1^{m+n} & -1^{m+n} & \dots & -1^{m+n} \\ \cdot & & & \\ \cdot & & & \\ \cdot & & & \\ -1^{m+n} & -1^{m+n} & \dots & -1^{m+n} \end{pmatrix}, \text{ for all } m, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Then $\alpha_{mn}x_{mn} \notin \left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V$. Hence

$\left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V$ is not solid.

3.5. Proposition. The sequence space $\left[\chi_{fB_{\eta}^{\mu}}^{2q}, \|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^{\varphi} \right]^V$ is not monotone

Proof: The proof follows from Proposition 3.4.

A sequence $x = (x_{mn})$ is said to be φ -statistically convergent or s_{φ} -statistically convergent to 0 if for every $\epsilon > 0$,

$$\lim_{rs} \left| \left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_{\eta}^{\mu}(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \geq \epsilon \right\} \right| = 0$$

where the vertical bars indicates the number of elements in the enclosed set. In this case we write $s_\varphi - \lim x = 0$ or $x_{mn} \rightarrow 0 (s_\varphi)$ and $s_\varphi = \{x : \exists 0 \in \mathbb{R} : s_\varphi - \lim x = 0\}$.

3.6. Proposition. For any sequence of Musielak Orlicz functions $f = (f_{mn})$ and $q = (q_{mn})$ be double analytic sequence of strictly positive real numbers. Then

$$\left[\chi_{fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V \subset \left[s_{\varphi fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V.$$

Proof: Let $x \in \left[\chi_{fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$ and $\epsilon > 0$. Then

$$\left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \geq \left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \geq \epsilon \right\}$$

from which it follows that $x \in \left[s_{\varphi fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$.

To show that $\left[s_{\varphi fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$ strictly contain $\left[\chi_{fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$. We define $x = (x_{mn})$ by $(x_{mn}) = mn$ if $rs - [\sqrt{\varphi rs}] + \leq mn \leq rs$ and $(x_{mn}) = 0$ otherwise. Then

$x \notin \left[\chi_{fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$ and for every $\epsilon (0 < \epsilon \leq 1)$,

$$\left\{ \left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \geq \epsilon \right\} = \frac{[\sqrt{\varphi rs}]}{\varphi rs} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } r, s \rightarrow \infty$$

i.e $x \rightarrow 0 \left(\left[s_{\varphi fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V \right)$, where $[\]$ denotes the greatest integer function. On the other hand,

$$\left[f_{mn} \left(\|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p \right) \right]^{q_{mn}} \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } r, s \rightarrow \infty$$

i.e $x_{mn} \not\rightarrow 0 \left[\chi_{fB_\eta^\mu}^{2q}, \|B_\eta^\mu(x), (d(x_1, 0), d(x_2, 0), \dots, d(x_{n-1}, 0))\|_p^\varphi \right]^V$. This completes the proof.

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